

THE PRONUNCIATION IN THE FORMAL SPOKEN PRACTICE OF THE MODERN MACEDONIAN LANGUAGE

Violeta Janusheva¹

“St. Kliment Ohridski” University,
Republic of Macedonia

Abstract:

The stress of the words, accentual units and the clitic expressions is among the most specific features in the Macedonian modern language, thus, it is very important to keep their pronunciation in accordance with the standard norm, especially in the formal communication. Therefore, the paper examines the formal spoken practice of the Macedonian standard language regarding the correct pronunciation of the words, accentual units and clitic expression and indicates the deviations from the language norm, which, on a long term, can jeopardize it and impose the incorrect pronunciation as correct one.

The research has qualitative paradigm and descriptive design. The sample of the formal spoken practice consists of television advertisements that contain speech acts in which the correct pronunciation of the words, accentual units and clitic expressions can be clearly heard. The television advertisements are chosen because they are a vital part of the visual media, thus, as other media content (visual or printed) have the obligation to keep, preserve and affirm the standard language norm regarding the pronunciation. The advertisements are broadcasted on the National television and on private televisions in the West dialectal region in the Republic of Macedonia. The research has also quantitative paradigm, i.e. it shows the attitudes and thoughts of 100 native Macedonian speakers on the pronunciation that occurs in the advertisements and in other forms of formal communication. These attitudes and thoughts are collected through a survey, which contains of three questions. The methods used are analysis, synthesis and comparison.

Surprisingly, the research results are very satisfactory. Regarding the analyzed advertisements, broadcasted on the private televisions in the West dialectal region in the Republic of Macedonia, there are no mistakes in the pronunciation of the words, accentual units and clitic expressions. However, three of the analyzed advertisements, broadcasted on the private televisions in the capital of the Republic of Macedonia, still show severe

¹ Correspondence: email violetajanuseva@gmail.com

deviations from the pronunciation norm. The reason for this can be found in the closeness of the West dialectal region with the norms of the modern Macedonian language, i.e. the dialects from this region are the foundation of the modern Macedonian language.

Keywords: Macedonian language, pronunciation, accentual units, clitic expressions

1. Introduction

The language is the most sophisticated mean, a system of signs that serves the communication of the people. Every language represents the identity of one nation. Therefore, every segment of the language in various spheres of the human acting and functioning should be preserved and kept in accordance with the standard language norm. This is especially relevant for the pronunciation of the words, accentual units and the clitic expression, because it represents the most significant feature of the Macedonian language. There are many rules for the pronunciation of the words, accentual units and clitic expressions in the Orthography of the Macedonian language (2015, pp. 27–36). Still the spoken practice is overloaded with incorrect pronunciation of the words, foreign as well as domestic, and especially of the accentual units and clitic expressions, even in formal situation where such pronunciation should not be allowed.

The correct or incorrect pronunciation of the words, accentual units and clitic expressions can easily be followed on numerous televisions and radio programs. Since the media represent the formal communication, they should reflect the language-spoken norm, to preserve it and to contribute to its affirmation.

Regarding the modern Macedonian language, the stress and pronunciation are studied within the phonetics and phonology. The modern Macedonian language has a dynamic accent, which means that one syllable from the word is pronounced higher. According to the place of the accent, the modern Macedonian language has a determined accent always on the third syllable from the end of the word in the words that have three or more syllables, such as *m'asata* [the table], *pr'odavach* [a salesperson], *kn'igata* [the book], *slatk'arnica* [a pastry shop], *slatkarn'icata* [the pastry shop] etc.

The words that have two syllables have accent on the second syllable from the end of the word, like *m'asa* [a table], *k'ukja* [a house], *gl'eda* [to see] etc.

The words that have one syllable have the accent on the only syllable in the word, like *m'al* [small], *b'el* [white], *v'rv* [a pick] etc.

This is the general rule, and it is applicable on domestic and on foreign words. However, regarding the foreign words they are classified into two categories. The first consists of foreign words that have accepted the Macedonian accent. For example, *b'iznis* [a

business], *d'irektor* [a principal], *m'obilen* [mobile] etc. The second category consists of words that have kept their original accent, i.e. the accent from the language they origin from. For example, *kompj'uter* [a computer], *literat'ura* [a literature], *nacion'alen* [national] etc. (Orthography of the Macedonian language, 2015, pp. 27–36).

The accentual units consist of two words, which have their own accent, but when they form accentual unit, they gain a new meaning that is not connected with the meaning of its components. There are several types of these accentual units, which depends on the nature of the words that formed accentual units. For example, the words *k'iselo* [sour] and *ml'eko* [milk] have their own accent and their own meaning. However, when they formed accentual units they gain a new meaning *kisel'o-mleko* [one type of yogurt]. This accentual unit is treated as one word and is pronounced with one stress, which according to the standard norm of the Macedonian language is on the third syllable from the end of the word. This accentual unit consists of an adjective and a noun. Another example is the accentual unit that consists of a number and a noun. The number and the noun have their own stress, *p'et* [five] and *p'ari* [money]. When forming the accentual unit, they are pronounced with one stress, which in the Macedonian language is on the third syllable from the end of the word, and gain a new meaning *p'et-pari n'e-davam z'a-nego* [I do not care about him]. This type of accentual units can consist of words that do not change their meaning when forming an accentual unit. For example, in the accentual units, which consist of a question word and a noun, there are two possibilities. The question word and the noun can form accentual units. Then they follow the rule in the Macedonian language and have the stress on the third syllable from the end of the word. In addition, there is a possibility for the question word and the noun not to form an accentual unit, thus, the two words have their own stress. For example, one can pronounce *k'oi-deca* [which children] where the accentual unit is considered as one word and has the stress on the third syllable from the end of the word. However, there is an option to pronounce the two words with their own accent in order logically to stress the meaning of the two words, thus, not forming an accentual unit, for example, *k'oi de'ca* (Orthography of the Macedonian language, 2015: 27–36)

The clitic expressions, on the other side, consist of one word, which does not have its own stress (clitic) and a word, which has its own stress. Then the word without a stress is connected with the word that has a stress and together they form a clitic expression. The words which do not have their own stress in the Macedonian language are the auxiliary verb *sum* [to be] in all persons and tenses, the particles *da, ne, kje, bi* [yes, no, will, would], the conjunctions, the prepositions and the short forms for direct and indirect object from the personal pronouns. There are two types of clitic expressions. The first type is the clitic expressions that consist of a clitic + a verb and in this case, the accent is always on the verb, if the verb has two syllables, for example, *mu-r'ekov* [I told him], *bi-mu-go-d'al* [I would give

him]. If the verb has three or more syllables, the stress is on the verb, according to the rule that in the Macedonian language the stress has to be on the third syllable from the end of the word. If the verb is in negative form, then the stress is always on the clitics, except when the verb has three syllables. For example, *n'e-vidov* [I did not see], *ne-bi-mu-g'o-rekol* [I would not tell him]. The second type is the clitic expressions that consist of a clitic + a noun. In this case, there are two possibilities. One is that the accent transfers on the clitic word like *n'a-drvo* [on the tree], *z'a-tebe* [for you]. The second possibility refers to the cases when the stress stays on the noun, because of many reasons, for example, *od-Sk'opje do-B'itola* [from Skopje to Bitola], *i-vo-p'etok* [and on Friday] (Orthography of the Macedonian language, 2015: 27–36).

2. Background information

In the broader sense of the term, the advertisements are forms of action upon one person with the use of the means for communications in order to achieve a previously settled goal. In a narrow sense, the advertisements are elements of the communicative system of the marketing and their final aim is to sell a product. The advertisements draw the public's attention and their stimulating function is above the informative. They stress the commercial moment. The advertisements affect the addressees not only with the arguments but also with their direction to cause empathy, i.e. to impact their feelings. The information about the product is put on the second place. The advertisements of the products are very important, and several significant steps have to be taken into account, such as analysis of the company, the market, the customers' spending power, the competitors' weaknesses and strengths, the partnerships etc. However, many of the people working with advertisements forget that the language is the base of the commercial. Thus, it needs to be considered in the advertisements as a relevant part.

The advertisements have several specific features, such as they present non-personal communication, their aim is toward persuasion of the public, they refer to public domain and someone has to pay for them. The advantage of the advertisements is that they reach to a broader public and thus, have a great control over the announcement. The disadvantages can be seen in the following: the advertisement process is a hard one, a lot of money is needed for their presentation on televisions and the danger of not making a mutual relation between the clients and the products is always a threat.

In the essay "The Language of Advertising Claims", J. Schrank, (1976) states that "the simplest and most direct way to study ads is through an analysis of the language of the advertising claim" and that the other aspects of the advertisement revolve around the language. Schrank also states that a simple analysis of the language used in the advertisements can show which

statements are false and which actually provide valuable information. Unfortunately, most of the advertisements belong in the category of pseudo-informative statements. They do not lie about the characteristics of the product, but they do not tell the truth either. Schrank says, “...they balance on the narrow line between truth and falsehood by a careful choice of words”.

Janusheva & Dimovska (2016: 42–52), examine the Macedonian language used in the advertisements and show many advertisements’ language characteristics on various levels, the orthographical, morphological, lexical and syntactical, that is used in combination with marketing components in order to make the ads successful and the product acknowledged. They also conducted a research, which displays language characteristics that are desirable in an advertisement and the language that native speakers of Macedonian favor. Their research show that for approximately 35% of the examinees the language used in the message is the first thing that attracts their attention; for 95% the language used in the advertisement is of a great relevance and for 85% of the interviewee the use of the standard Macedonian language should be promoted.

The media are extremely important because the incorrect pronunciation can easily be accepted as correct one. Many scientific workers stress the relevance of the correct pronunciation, which occurs in the media. In the interview with our distinguished professor, Lidija Tanturovska, she suggests that many mistakes in all language levels are present in the public speaking, and that they should not occur. She underlines that this happens due to many influences and they change the shape and image of the Macedonian language. Among others, she confirms that the correct pronunciation is very important in our language and indicates the mistakes regarding the pronunciation of the accentual units and clitic expressions. This leads to change of the intonation and deviation from the standard norm. According to her, the frequent use of the incorrect pronunciation, after a while can become dominant and suppresses the correct pronunciation, thus the wrong pronunciation can be easily accepted instead of the correct one. She states that the language norm should be addressed as a law, which should be respected (Dimitrijevska, 31.3.2014).

3. Methodology of the research

Bearing in mind the specific features of the advertisements and the relevance of correct pronunciation of the words, accentual units and clitic expressions in the spirit of the Macedonian standard language’s norm, the research analyses several advertisements. The advertisements are registered within the period from June 27 till July 12, 2017 on the following televisions: Macedonian national television and the local private televisions: TV „Sitel“ [TV “Sitel”], Nasha TV [Our TV], Alfa TV, TV “Nova” [TV New], 24vesti [24 news]. The advertisements are tape-recorded and transcript. In the paper, only excerpts from the

transcripts relevant for the pronunciation are given. These excerpts contain words, accentual units and clitic expressions that are subject of the analysis.

The research has qualitative paradigm and descriptive design. The sample of the formal spoken practice consists of television advertisements that contain speech acts in which the correct or incorrect pronunciation of the words, accentual units and clitic expressions can be clearly heard. The television advertisements are chosen because they are a vital part of the visual media, thus as other media content (visual or printed) have the obligation to keep, preserve and affirm the standard language norm regarding the pronunciation. The advertisements are broadcasted on the National television and on several private televisions in the West dialectal region in the Republic of Macedonia. The research has also quantitative paradigm, i.e. it shows the attitudes and thoughts of 100 native Macedonian speakers on the pronunciation that occurs in the advertisements and in other forms of formal communication. These attitudes and thoughts are collected through a survey, which contains three questions. The methods used are analysis, synthesis and comparison. The accentual units are given in italic, while the clitic expressions are underlined.

4. Results and Discussion

On June 27, 2017 at 16:03, on Alfa TV, the following advertisement is registered: *Otsega, nova doza na semejno osvezhuvanje... super cena za sekoj den da bide povkusen* [From now on, new dose of family refreshment... great price for every day to be more tasteful]. This advertisement shows that all of the words and the clitic expressions are pronounced according to the norms of the standard Macedonian language. Though the words *sekoj* [every] and *den* [day], can form an accentual unit, in the advertisement they are pronounced as *s'ekoj d'en* with stress on every word. Thus, the words do not form accentual unit. This is probably because of the aim of the advertisement, namely to underline the meaning of every word and this is in accordance with the Macedonian language's norm. The same advertisement can be heard on the television 24vesti [24news].

On June 27, 2017 at 16:45, on TV "Nova" [TV "New"], the following advertisement is evidenced: *Izraboteni od visokokvaliteten pamuk, sozdadeni za dolgogodishna upotreba. *Ova leto* uzhivajte vo mekosta i prefinetosta na proizvodite od poznatiot brend „Frotirka“, edinstveno vo Tineks [Made from high quality cotton, and created for long lasting use. This summer enjoy the softness and elegance of the products from the well-known brand "Frotirka", only in Tinex]. All of the words and clitic expressions are pronounced with a correct stress. The words *ova* [this] and *leto* [summer] can form an accentual unit, which consists of a pronoun word and a noun. However, in the advertisement, they are*

pronounced as separate words with their own stress. This means that they do not form an accentual unit and the advertiser wants to highlight the meaning of every word, which is in accordance with the Macedonian language's norm.

On June 27, 2017 at 16:57, on TV "Nova" [TV "New"] this advertisement is registered: Tvojot nov dom, toa si ti. Apliciraj za stanben kredit po tvoja mera... Bez provizija za odobruvanje, troshoci... banka na vasheto semejstvo [Your home is you. Apply for a mortgage tailored specially for you... Without provision for permission, costs for... bank of your family]. In this advertisement, all the words and clitic expressions are pronounced correctly. The words *tvoja* [yours] and *mera* [measure] can form an accentual unit, which consists of a pronoun word and a noun, with the meaning *tailored by your needs*. However, as said above, here the meaning of the two words is pointed out, thus, they do not form an accentual unit. This advertisement can also be heard on the National television.

On June 27, 2017 at 16:57, on TV "Nova" [TV "New"], the following advertisement is broadcasted: Specijalizirani prodavnici za zdrava i organska hrana. Golem asortiman na organska hrana i širok spektar na dodatoci vo ishranata, bezglutenska i veganska hrana, organski vitamini, bez genetski modificirani organizmi... specijalizirani prodavnici na Zegin za organska i zdrava hrana [Specialized markets for healthy and organic food. Great assortment of organic food and a wide spectrum of food's supplements, non- gluten and vegan food, organic vitamins, without modified organisms... specialized markets of Zegin for organic and healthy food]. The analysis shows that all of the words and clitic expressions are pronounced in accordance with the Macedonian language's norm. Accentual units are not present in this excerpt.

The advertisement broadcasted on June 27, 2017 at 16:58, on TV "Nova" [TV "New"] is: Omileno mesto za ljubitelite na gastronomskite zadovolstva... sekoj obrok isprepletuva zhivopisna niza od chuvstva... a vrvot na zadovolstvata se vistinskite amerikanski burgeri... Elit, stek haus, ve ocekuvame [A favorite place for the fans of gastronomic pleasures... every meal interweaves a pictorial sequence of feelings... and the pick of the pleasures are the real American burgers... Elite steak house, we expect you]. The analysis shows that all of the words and clitic expressions used in this advertisement are pronounced with the correct stress. The words *s'ekoj* [every] and *'obrok* [meal] in this advertisement do not form an accentual unit because the advertisement intends to display the meaning of every word.

On July 8, 2017 at 19:45, on TV "Sitel" this advertisement is evidenced: So Koka-kola do nezaboravno leto. Pronajdi go kodot... i doznaj dali si dobitnik na edna od mnogute kul nagradi ili, pak, na nezaboravno patovanje na edna od fenomenalnite destinacii [With Coca Cola to unforgettable summer. Find the code... and reveal whether you get one of the many cool awards or an unforgettable journey on one of the phenomenal destinations]. All the

words and clitic expressions are pronounced in accordance with the Macedonian standard language's norm. There are no accentual units in this excerpt.

The advertisement registered on July 8, 2017 at 17:31 on Nasha TV (Our TV) is: So dvanasetgodishno iskustvo Rojalplast pretstavuva kompanija so profesionalen tim, vrven kvalitet, usluga i inovativni proizvodi... Vashite baranja kje ja dobijat maksimalnata vrednost... Vashiot proveren partner [With twelve-year experience, Royalplast presents a company with professional team, ultimate quality, service and innovative products... your requests will get maximal value... your identified partner... The analysis shows that all of the words and the clitic expressions are pronounced in accordance with the Macedonian language's standard norm. There are no accentual units in this excerpt.

The advertisement evidenced on Nasha TV [Our TV] on July 8, 2017 at 17:42 is: ...Vo kompanijata se raboti profesionalno i kvalitetno so najsovremena tehnologija... Denes, kompanijata mozhe da se pofali so imponzanten asortiman na sekakov vid vrati i prozorci. ...Podelete go so nas vedriot pogled na idninata... Niprom Strumica [...The company works professionally. With quality and most sophisticated technology... Today, the company can praise the impuissant assortment of various types of doors and windows... Share with us the bright view toward the future... Niprom Strumica]. The analysis shows that in this advertisement all the words and clitic expressions are pronounced correctly. Accentual units are not present in this excerpt

The excerpt registered on TV "Sitel" on July 10, 2017 at 20:39 is: Vo srceto na Ohrid naskoro, povekje od pedeset prodavnici, restorani ... Kam vilidzh, noviot centar na gradot. [In the heart of Ohrid soon, more than fifty stores, restaurants... the new center of the town, Kam Village]. All the words and clitic expressions are pronounced correctly. The words *noviot* [the new] and *centar* [center] can form an accentual units that consists of a pronoun word and a noun. However, in this excerpt, they are pronounced as two separate words with their own stress, thus not forming an accentual unit. It is likely that the intention of the advertisement is to stress the meaning of the two words logically, which is in accordance with the Macedonian language's norm.

Three advertisements are evidenced on the National television, and on private televisions: 24vesti [24news], on July 9, 2017 at 20:30; on July 9, 2017 at 21:20 and on Alfa TV on July 9, 2017 at 22:45. They refer to two well-known Macedonian brands of beer: "Skopsko" [Beer named by the capital of the Republic of Macedonia, Skopje] and "Zlaten dab" [Golden oak]. In the complete advertisements, the words, accentual units and clitic expressions are pronounced correctly. Suddenly, at the very end of the advertisements one can hear only one sentence that ruins the whole impression of these advertisements regarding the pronunciation. In the first excerpt, the advertisement ends with the sentence: Skopsko – za nas [Skopsko – for us]. The two words *za* [for] and *nas* [us] are pronounced

with their own stress, though they should form a clitic expression, which contains of a preposition and a pronoun word, in this case, it is the long form for the direct object from the personal pronoun *nie* [we]. In the Macedonian language, the preposition and the pronoun always form a clitic expression with the stress before the vowel of the preposition. The pronunciation of this clitic expression as two separate words is considered as a severe deviation from the spoken language's norm, because the clitic forms, including the preposition, do not have their own accent and thus, the preposition have to form a clitic expression. The same happens with the sentences: *Sega znaesh deka ovoj Dab e za tebe* [Now you know that this Oak is for you] and *Sto i edna prichina, edno pivo, za nas* [One hundred and one reason – one beer, for us]. The clitic expressions *za-tebe* [for you] and *za-nas* [for us] are pronounced as words with separate stress and this should not be allowed.

The analyzed excerpts confirm that the situation in the formal spoken practice of the Macedonian language, regarding the advertisements, cannot be evaluated as completely bad. This rather means that the persons who read the advertisements are fully aware that they speak in public and that they should contribute to preservation of the Macedonian language's norm, especially regarding the most relevant feature, i.e. the pronunciation of the words, accentual units and clitic expressions. In addition, the analyzed excerpts show that the advertisements have one very relevant issue regarding the pronunciation of the accentual units. The pronunciation indicates that two words, which will usually form accentual units in the informal spoken practice, in the advertisement are pronounced with a stress on every word. This occurs because one of the very specific characteristic of the advertisement is to stress logically the meaning of the two words, and this imposes itself like a very relevant request for the advertisement to sound more convincing.

Though these deviations from the spoken norm are strange and a little bit odd, they can be explained. These deviations are noticed on the National television and on two private televisions located in the capital of the Republic of Macedonia. This region is known as a region, which as a result from the migrations from smaller towns to the capital, and the closeness to the Serbian border, where many influences can be observed. Thus, these deviations are seen as specific features of the speech in the capital. However, because of the increased concentration of various citizens from smaller towns, it is most probable that these deviations will import in the speech of these citizens and they will bring these newly gained deviations in their regions when return. Moreover, because the capital's speech is seen as a prestigious one, step by step, these deviations can become a regularly phenomenon and suppress the correct pronunciation. This is in accordance with the notice mentioned above (Dimitrijevska, 31.3.2014).

As for the results from the survey, it can be said that they are directed toward the preservation and affirmation of the Macedonian language spoken norm. All three questions

were answered by all of the participants. The answers of the question: Do the incorrect pronunciation of the words in the media bother you?, indicate that the Macedonians are concerned for their native language. All of the participants, state that they are bothered if heard an incorrect pronunciation in the media, because, according to them, the audio and visual media should mostly be dedicated to correct pronunciation, thus, undertake any measure to ensure the correct pronunciation and affirmation of the language. Some of the answers are: We have a beautiful language; Wrong pronunciation affects even the beauty of the product; Visual media should take care of the standard Macedonian language; The incorrect pronunciation can be adopted as correct one. The answers of the question: Who makes more mistakes regarding the pronunciation on the media, the interviewers or the interviewees?, suggest that Macedonians are aware of the deviations and can make clear distinction. All participants confirm that the deviations from the pronunciation norm are present more in the speech of the interviewees rather than in the speech of the interviewers. This clearly indicates that the interviewers take into consideration that their speech is a public one. Therefore, they pay attention on the pronunciation of their own speech, trying to keep it in accordance with the language's norm. Some of the answers are: The interviewees make more mistakes; The interviewers are more correct in their pronunciation; Some of the guests in various programs forget that their speech addresses a broader audience which is well educated and notice their deviations; Some of the interviewees speak as they are at home and do not worry about the pronunciation. For God sakes, they are on TV; Are these people uneducated? Why are they using a wrong pronunciation? Have not they been told that they make mistake? The answers of the question: Which group of people is most prone to the deviation in pronunciation on the media?, show that there is a need of further elaboration of the pronunciation. All participants claim that the politicians are the group of people who most deviate from the pronunciation norm. This is a clear indicator for the general picture in the Macedonian society. Most of the people watch political programs, and the language of the politicians is constantly present in our media. Thus, it is something that is heard most frequently and the deviations are easy noticeable. Most of the politicians deviate even of the well-established pronunciation of the words, and introduce in their public speech elements from the region they come from. This way, they seriously jeopardize the language's norm and contribute to the deforming of the Macedonian language.

5. Conclusion

The conclusion is more than evident. The formal spoken practice seen through the prism of the advertisements can be evaluated as good. Even a relevant feature of the advertisement becomes known through the analysis, i.e. words, which will usually form accentual unit, do

not form such unit in the advertisements. The two words are rather pronounced with a separate accent, thus indicating that the advertisements want to stress logically the meaning of every word. This insures the convincing function of the advertisements. The only three deviations found in the advertisements may seem as unimportant, irrelevant and the one that cannot harm the language pronunciation norm. However, these three deviations refer to a relevant feature of the Macedonian language that can enforce the incorrect pronunciation instead of the correct one and broaden this incorrectness to a large number of words, accentual units and clitic expressions, thus, create an illusion that the pronunciation is correct. Thus, it can be concluded that everyone included in reading the advertisements, or posing questions to someone, on the media, has to be completely aware of the pronunciation of his speech. Moreover, this issue has to be address seriously and thus, needs further research of the reasons for such deviations.

References

1. Dimitrijevska, A. (31.3.2014). Interview with Lidija Tanturovska. Vo Skopje sekoj zboruva kako shto saka [In Skopje everyone speaks the way he likes]. <http://mrt.com.mk/node/6767>, 21.7.2017
2. Grupa avtori. (2015). Pravopis na makedonskiot jazik [The Orthography of the Macedonian language]. Skopje: Institut za makedonski jazik "K. Misirkov"
3. Janusheva, V., Dimovska, A. (2016). Standard Macedonian language used in television advertisements. North Western University "Neofit Rilsky", *Philological faculty – Blagoevgrad, Orbis Linguarum*, 14 (2): 45–52
4. Schrank, J. (1976). The Language of Advertising Claims. Teaching about Doublespeak. Illinois: NCTE

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). and European Journal of Literature, Language and Linguistics Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).